

Self-Efficacy and Attitude of The Senior High School Learners in the Specialized Subjects of Humanities and Social Sciences Strand in Tuao High School

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ABSTRACT

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Students' self-efficacy and attitudes are crucial in the field of Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS). When students approach these disciplines with optimism and a strong belief in their capabilities, they tend to find learning more accessible and enjoyable. This study evaluated the self-efficacy and attitude toward HUMSS-specialized subjects among the Senior High School students in Tuao High School for the school year 2023-2024. It employed the embedded design and assessed four sources of self-efficacy: mastery experience, social persuasion, vicarious experience, physiological and emotional states, and overall attitude levels. It also compared these factors across various student profiles and examined the correlation between self-efficacy and attitudes. Utilizing a modified questionnaire for self-efficacy and the Modified Fennema-Sherman Attitude Scales for attitudes, results showed high self-efficacy and moderately favorable attitudes toward specialized subjects. No significant differences were observed based on sex, birth order, or monthly family income. However, a significant relationship was noted between self-efficacy and attitudes towards these subjects. Further research into the long-term impact of self-efficacy and attitudes can inform educational practices, leading to targeted interventions, personalized teaching methods, and enhanced teacher training, promoting academic and career success.

KEYWORDS:

Fennema-Sherman, motivation, perspective, self-confidence, self-esteem, sources of self-efficacy

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

The Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand in Senior High School education is one of the strands under the Academic track based on the Improved Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act 10533), which established K-12 as a legal framework. It is a comprehensive educational overhaul designed to cater to student's unique abilities, interests, and potential (Government of the Philippines, 2012). The law sought to enhance the curriculum and lengthen the required years of fundamental education. The Senior High School has been added because of this educational reform. The revised curriculum added two exit points: employment and

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entrepreneurship, aiming to allow Filipino students to learn the knowledge and skills required for a bachelor's degree (Estrera, 2020; ICEF Monitor, 2013). Each track has its own set of Applied Track Subjects and Specialized Subjects.

Specialized subjects are subjects tailored to the learning strand or career path selected by the students. They are akin to the core courses typically undertaken by college students, albeit designed to be more straightforward than their collegiate equivalents (Senior High School in the Philippines: Curriculum Breakdown – Courses in the Philippines: College, TESDA, Online, Short Courses, 2018).

The HUMSS strand is important in shaping students' understanding of the human experience and societal structures. It aims to create citizens who are critical thinkers, socially responsible, and knowledgeable of the world (AMAOEd 2021). Based on SEAMO-INNOTECH (2012), as cited by Estrera (2020), among these are learning how to think creatively and logically, considering one's own culture, performing good research and idea exchange, being

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accountable and effective, being ecologically conscious, and having a global perspective are all essential. Hence, the researcher wanted to look into the self-efficacy and attitude towards humanities and social sciences. Their motivation towards the humanities and the social sciences is an important element in helping students be critical, creative thinkers and socially responsible.

Some studies looked into self-efficacy, especially by researchers who observed low achievements among students. For example, Rahemi (2007) studied the low English achievements of Iranian high school students majoring in Humanities. The study found that humanities major students had a very weak self-efficacy in English and held negative beliefs about their academic capacity as foreign language learners. It discovered a positive correlation between their achievements in English as a Foreign Language and self-efficacy.

In the recent study by Gordon et al. (2024), it was mentioned that little is known about how reforms in education have improved schooling and how these have influenced pre-service teachers' self-efficacy. The findings emphasized the role of enacted mastery and vicarious experiences in improving self-efficacy.

The above study supports the study of Ifamuyiwa et al. (2024). They concluded that cognitive, emotional, and behavioral management are good predictors of the self-efficacy and attitude of male and female secondary students in mathematics. Hence, they recommended that the Nigerian education stakeholders ensure that students are engaged cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally in self-efficacy and that their attitude toward mathematics will be increased.

Further, self-efficacy and attitude are predictive factors for student achievement based on the study of Roebianto (2020), who examined the impact of Indonesian students' attitudes and self-efficacy on their achievement in Science, revealing that both factors significantly influence students' academic success in the subject, and the study of Zhu & Luo (2024), results highlight intricate motivational profiles that influence science achievement, necessitating customized support in identity safety and self-efficacy.

In Social Studies, Kılıçoğlu (2018) investigated the self-efficacy and motivation of secondary school students in their social studies courses. The findings indicate that intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and academic achievement factors collectively predict students' levels of self-efficacy in social studies, accounting for 64% of the variance in self-efficacy levels.

With the above studies, this research study determined the correlation between students' self-efficacy and attitude toward the HUMSS-specialized subjects in Tuao High School. It is highlighted by recent research primarily focusing on self-efficacy in diverse educational

contexts, including language learning (Rahemi, 2007), teacher education reforms (Gordon et al., 2024), and mathematics education (Ifamuyiwa et al., 2024). While these studies offer valuable insights into how self-efficacy impacts academic achievement and the importance of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects, there remains a distinct gap concerning the Humanities and Social Sciences strand, specifically within senior high school education. Current literature predominantly addresses STEM fields and general academic environments (Roebianto, 2020; Zhu & Luo, 2024; Kılıçoğlu, 2018), underscoring the need to explore how self-efficacy and attitudes influence academic outcomes within the Humanities and Social Sciences. Addressing this gap aims to provide tailored insights that can inform educational approaches and initiatives aimed at enhancing student engagement, motivation, and academic success in these specialized subjects at Tuao High School.

Tuao High School is the lone Secondary School of the Bagabag II of the Schools Division of Nueva Vizcaya. It is classified as a medium school, with 401 students enrolled from grade 7 to grade 12 and 18 Faculty and staff members, including the School Head, for the School Year 2022-2023. The Senior High School recently introduced the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) Strand, with 88 students enrolled in Grades 11 and 12.

The researcher observed that the SHS students at Tuao High School showed less interest in or what appeared to be a negative attitude toward the HUMSS-specialized subjects. When asked about concepts or ideas relevant to social studies, which has been covered in Junior High School Araling Panlipunan, learners have no prior understanding of those topics in social studies. She also noticed that females have a more positive attitude and sense of self-efficacy regarding HUMSS-related subjects.

Tuao High School offers Philippine Politics and Governance (PPG) in Grade 11 for the first semester and Disciplines and Ideas in the Social Sciences (DISS) for the second semester. PPG course provides students with an overview of fundamental concepts and key components of politics and governance, approached from a historical-institutional perspective. It delves into the evolution of our nation's political institutions, procedures, and relationships over time. Additionally, the course aims to enhance students' civic competency by deepening their understanding of both personal and societal rights and responsibilities. On the other hand, the DISS course introduces fundamental concepts, methods of inquiry, and subjects within the Social Sciences. It explores significant thinkers and their ideas within these fields, drawing connections to the Philippine context and contemporary global developments.

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And for Grade 12, it offers Creative Writing (CW) and Disciplines and Ideas in the Applied Social Sciences (DIASS). The Creative Writing course aims to help Grade 12 students improve their reading, writing, and creative skills. It also introduces them to the basic principles of writing fiction, poetry, and drama. It discusses how well-known authors across a range of genres have used these principles. Each lesson will focus on analyzing writing methods and workshopping student drafts to improve their manuscripts. The ability to mix inspiration with revision is taught to students, along with the development of form.

The DIASS course introduces several applied social sciences, such as counseling, social work, and communication, which are rooted in the principles of psychology, sociology, anthropology, and other related social sciences. This course highlights the interconnectedness of various applied social science disciplines. It focuses on their methodologies and applications in key development sectors (Department of Education, 2016).

Tuao High School's recent introduction of the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) Strand marks a significant shift from the General Academic Strand (GAS) in its Senior High School curriculum. This change reflects a strategic move towards offering specialized subjects that cater to its students' specific academic interests and career aspirations. The School Head emphasizes the importance of continuously updating and expanding the range of specialized subjects within the HUMSS Strand to meet the needs of enrolled students fully.

In light of this transformation, a pressing need arises to conduct a comprehensive study. This study aims to serve as a foundational resource for shaping the curriculum and instructional approaches for the newly introduced specialized subjects. By conducting such research, the school can gather valuable insights into the academic preferences, learning styles, and career goals of students opting for the HUMSS Strand.

The study will also focus on identifying current trends and emerging areas within the humanities and social sciences that are of particular relevance to the local community and the broader society. This understanding will enable Tuao High School to tailor its curriculum to ensure it remains contemporary, engaging, and aligned with both academic standards and the evolving needs of students and the community.

Furthermore, the findings of this study will provide a basis for strategic decision-making regarding resource allocation, faculty development, and infrastructure enhancements necessary to support the effective delivery of specialized subjects within the HUMSS Strand. By leveraging empirical data and student feedback, the school can implement targeted interventions that enhance learning

outcomes and foster academic excellence among its students.

Hence, the proposed study represents a proactive approach by Tuao High School to optimize the implementation of the HUMSS Strand. It underscores the school's commitment to providing quality education that not only meets regulatory requirements but also empowers students to thrive in their chosen fields of study and contribute meaningfully to society. By investing in research-driven curriculum development, Tuao High School positions itself as a leader in senior high school education, dedicated to nurturing well-rounded individuals equipped for the challenges of the modern world.

Given the above literature and studies on self-efficacy and attitude, as well as the current observations about the humanities and social studies, this study determined the relationships of these variables to the specialized subjects. Hence, this study.

Concepts of Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy is confidence in one's ability to navigate the problems life presents successfully. This significantly impacts an individual's sense of self-worth and the capacity to succeed in the long run (Grantt, 2014). Self-efficacy pertains to the belief in one's ability to learn or execute actions at specific levels. (Bandura, 1997; cited by Schunk and Dibenedetto, 2020). It is the confidence an individual has in their capacity to thrive in a specific circumstance. (Lopez-Garrido, 2023). Research over many years and thousands of studies has shown how important this belief is in achieving an individual's objectives (Celestine, 2019). In addition, Cherry (2023) relates it to an individual's confidence in their capacity to control their behavior, impact their environment, and sustain motivation towards their objectives.

Given the abovementioned definitions of self-efficacy, it can be stated that self-efficacy is not a one-situation, one-context belief in one's ability to achieve targets or objectives. As Cherry (2023) propounded, self-efficacy can manifest in various contexts. Hence, it can be manifested in politics, business, and education, among many others.

In the field of education, students are believed to accomplish more if they have high self-efficacy in as much as self-efficacy greatly affects their mental health, motivation, and performance as well as the behavior they choose to engage in and how they respond to their environment (Breker, 2015; as cited by Schunk and Dibenedetto, 2020).

For instance, the study by Zelenak (2019) demonstrated that the Music Performance Self-Efficacy Scale responses indicated self-efficacy, while audition scores indicated achievement. He further stated that

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enactive mastery experience exhibited the strongest correlation with the overall concept of self-efficacy, consistent with other studies.

Furthermore, Fuchs (2005), quoted by Probstl and Schmidt-Honig (2019), discussed the idea of self-efficacy in its practical application and defined it as the capacity of an individual to act out of their motivation and influence anything. He noted that future tasks are also affected by how one's self-efficacy is perceived. Therefore, those with strong self-efficacy are more likely to embrace difficult circumstances and treat them with great devotion and entailment.

Moreover, Bandura (1997), cited by Gale et al. (2021), proposed in the social cognitive theory that individuals assess their self-efficacy by considering information from four primary sources: enactive mastery experiences, where goals are achieved through direct action; vicarious experiences, involving observation of others including oneself in performing tasks; social persuasions, comprising messages from others that vary in impact based on content and source credibility; and physiological and affective states such as mood, stress, and anxiety. According to Bandura's model, these factors collectively shape how individuals perceive and evaluate their capabilities.

These four sources of self-efficacy are utilized collectively in self-evaluations. For instance, individuals integrate both their own direct experiences and observations of others when comparing themselves against perceived group norms. Understanding these sources and their interactions is crucial for enhancing results in education, employment, and personal growth, as well as for furthering comprehension of human behavior and psychology.

For example, in education, Zhang and Ardasheva's (2019) study on learners' self-efficacy in English public speaking found that aggregate data largely support Bandura's proposed sources of self-efficacy. Specifically, enactive mastery experiences (EME), vicarious experiences (VE), and social persuasions (VP) were significant predictors of self-efficacy among educational psychology students (EPS). However, physiological and affective states (PAS) did not show a significant unique contribution. Subsample analysis also revealed that variables such as prior educational psychology course experience, gender, and academic major could influence the strength and presence of the relationship between self-efficacy and its theoretical sources. This study underscores the variability in how the four sources of self-efficacy contribute to self-assessment.

Another is the study of Villas (2019), which assessed the self-efficacy of Grade 11 senior high school students in an urban School in the Philippines, focusing on academic and health components. Results showed students

have a moderate overall self-efficacy level, with significant differences observed between public and private school students in vicarious experience and verbal persuasion. Private school students scored higher in verbal persuasion, while public school students showed higher self-efficacy in vicarious experience. Differences across academic tracks were also noted in the verbal persuasion component.

Concepts of Attitude

In addition to self-efficacy, attitude is vital for the achievement of particular targets or objectives. It is the way that a person's propensity to react favorably or unfavorably to a particular concept, object, person, or circumstance. This reaction can be a person's implicit or explicit sentiment, either positive or negative, that might govern how they react to a situation, an idea, or other people (Hammad, 2016, as quoted by Mensah et al., 2023). It is frequently developed based on someone's experience and upbringing, and it can significantly impact how people behave and respond in different circumstances (Cherry, 2023). On the other hand, Montano and Kasprzyk (2008) stated by Wang (2020), contended that attitude is a structure that is tightly related to views about outcomes, meaning that someone who has a great attitude toward a certain behavior will have strong beliefs that the behavior will result in a favorable outcome.

Based on the above statement, a person's attitude changes depending on their circumstances or environment, and the success of one's performance heavily depends on their attitude toward the scenario. As John C. Maxwell (2003) states, it is one's attitude that determines his actions and, eventually, his accomplishments. Hence, the attitude may predict the successful performance of an individual. Researchers also contend that attitude can take on a variety of various forms.

In the field of education, students' attitudes can differ based on the subject they are studying. As a result, researchers assess their students' attitudes toward the subject or course they are teaching to cater to their expectations and make it more interesting to them.

For instance, Hwang and Son (2021) found a positive correlation between students' attitudes toward mathematics and their mathematics performance. Their findings suggested that students who enjoy studying mathematics and engage in related activities, those who believe in the positive outcomes of learning mathematics (such as academic success and job opportunities), and those who have confidence in their mathematical abilities are more likely to achieve higher results in mathematics. As a result, they recommended that educators assess students' attitudes toward mathematics and offer suitable support to foster the cultivation of a positive attitude toward mathematics. In addition, the study of Kiwanuka et al. (2020) examined the temporal association between attitudes

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toward mathematics and mathematics performance among first-year secondary school students, specifically focusing on gender disparities in Central Uganda. The study found evidence supporting both the self-enhancement model, where attitude influences achievement, and the skill-development model, where achievement influences attitude.

The study of Mazana et al. (2018) also delved into students' attitudes toward learning Mathematics. Several factors played a role in shaping students' learning and performance in mathematics, including students' attitudes towards the subject. The findings indicated that students initially held a favorable attitude toward mathematics. Still, this attitude tended to decline as they progressed to higher educational levels. Despite the small number, negative attitudes significantly impact students' learning outcomes. Thus, it should not be ignored, so they recommended that teachers should implement instructional strategies that address the diverse needs and potential barriers to learning among students. They advocated for techniques that reduce fear, stimulate active interest, and foster enjoyment in teaching-learning processes.

In the English field, the study of Yuliani et al. (2023) investigated the EFL students' attitudes toward English language learning. Their study demonstrated a favorable attitude towards learning the English language, with the findings indicating that this attitude significantly impacted students' achievements and motivation in English language learning.

Research in the Social Science discipline shows that students tend to harbor less favorable attitudes toward social studies subjects than other subjects. For example, the study of Dunder and Rapoport (2018) focused on upper elementary students' perceptions of social studies, science, and math. It aimed to determine if there were notable differences between the attitudes of 4th and 5th-grade students toward social studies. The findings revealed that students exhibited less positive attitudes towards social studies in comparison to science and mathematics.

Meanwhile, the study of Mensah (2020) investigated students' attitudes towards Social Studies learning and their academic performance within the Accra Metropolitan Assembly in the Greater Accra Region of Ghana. The findings revealed that students within this region demonstrated an average performance in Social Studies, alongside exhibiting positive attitudes towards the subject. Consequently, the recommendation was made for the Ghana Education Service to enlist qualified teachers specifically for teaching Social Studies in Senior High Schools. This strategic step is believed to facilitate students' improvement by providing them with the necessary expertise and guidance in Social Studies.

In the Philippines, the study by Benitez (2022) highlighted the importance of students' academic motivation and attitudes in their academic advancement, particularly in Social Studies. The research revealed that students generally maintained a "positive attitude" towards social studies. Furthermore, it demonstrated a noteworthy positive correlation between respondents' academic motivation and their attitude toward social studies.

Relationship between Self-efficacy and Attitude

The abovementioned studies looked into self-efficacy and attitude as separate variables. The bone of contention now is whether self-efficacy and attitude are positively correlated. The study of Yau and Leung (2018) examined the correlation between the two. Among 187 students enrolled in a higher education institution in Hong Kong, a study unveiled a positive and significant association between attitudes toward technology utilization and their self-efficacy.

Kundu and Ghose (2016) showed that students' attitudes about the study of mathematics significantly impacted their self-efficacy in a different study involving 784 students in India. Another is the study of Natividad et al. (2019), which evaluated 154 third-year high school students in a few regional studies and discovered a high correlation between self-efficacy and attitude. Lastly, the study by Repuya (2016) found that Mathematics self-efficacy and attitudes towards Mathematics were significantly correlated among the 35 students in Mathematics.

Relationship between self-efficacy, attitude, and profile variables

Some studies also looked into the relationships between self-efficacy, attitude, and demographic variables like sex, birth order, and family income. For instance, the study by Wen et al. (2020) discovered a strong relationship between family income and study attitude. They also discovered that home amenities, or assessing home-based material resources, played the most important mediating role in explaining the impacts of family income on cognitive ability and study attitude.

In terms of sex, Ayebo and Dingel (2021) discovered no statistically significant difference between men and women on the mathematics attitude scales, except for like, where males scored higher than women. In self-efficacy, the same result was obtained from the study of Villas (2019); there is no significant difference in self-efficacy of students across sexes. In contrast, findings from Reber et al.'s (2018) study underscored a substantial main effect of gender on various metrics, including mean mathematics self-efficacy scores, attitude scores, anxiety scores, and mathematics achievement. As a result,

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mathematics teachers must analyze methods and regulations to understand why there is a gender imbalance. There may be inadvertent educational techniques that contribute to the gender gap.

Another is about birth order. Effiong et al.'s (2023) research included sex and birth order as variables. In terms of birth order, firstborns had a more favorable attitude toward Mathematics than their other siblings, while in sex, male students had a more positive attitude toward Mathematics than their female counterparts. The study concluded that students' attitudes toward mathematics were influenced by birth order and gender in Eket, Nigeria. As a result, it was suggested that gender-sensitive mathematics teaching and evaluation methodologies be implemented to reduce gender-related bias and unfairness.

Recent studies show the relationship between self-efficacy and the said profile variables. In terms of sex, the study by Zelenak (2019) found that there is no difference when comparing the association between self-efficacy and achievement across age and gender classifications. Regarding self-efficacy and birth order, the findings of the study of Mazumdar & Sumathi (2022) show no significant difference in courage or self-efficacy based on birth order. This is because, in contrast to earlier times, all children, regardless of gender or birth order, are treated equally today. In terms of sex and family monthly income, the study by Christy & Mythili (2020) stated that females tended to exhibit higher levels of self-esteem, self-efficacy, and academic performance compared to males.

Additionally, family income was found to influence self-esteem levels. Moreover, the study highlighted a positive correlation between self-esteem, self-efficacy, and academic performance. Contrarily, findings from the study by Retutas and Rebio (2021) indicated that both family monthly income and gender showed no significant influence on students' self-efficacy levels, attitudes toward mathematics, or their academic performance in the subject.

Furthermore, Barrera's (2022) study, which sought to explore the correlation between academic resilience and self-efficacy among Grade 7 students enrolled in Social Studies at Calamba City Science Integrated School, unveiled that students demonstrate both academic resilience and self-efficacy, revealed that students exhibit academic resilience and self-efficacy. There is a significant relationship between students' academic resilience responses and their self-efficacy in Social Studies. However, no significant disparity was found when examining academic resilience and self-efficacy based on gender. Consequently, the study recommended the development of school programs aimed at nurturing and enhancing students' self-efficacy.

Based on the results of the research studies mentioned above and the researchers' observation, the researcher is motivated to measure the relationship between self-efficacy and the attitude of SHS students in humanities and social sciences strand specialized subjects at Tuao High School.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the social cognitive theory developed by Albert Bandura. It serves as the foundation of this work. It holds, as indicated by Nickerson 2023; Shunk (2012), that individuals have an active role in shaping their learning by assessing the results of their actions. This understanding thus changes the environment and a person's personality, influencing and molding subsequent conduct. Bandura (1986), as referenced by Cherry (2023), asserts that self-efficacy is a central concept in social cognitive theory. This theory emphasizes the importance of social interactions, observational learning, and reciprocal determinism in shaping one's personality. According to Bandura (1997), as mentioned by Bourne (2021), since people have the power to decide what they do, they are producers rather than merely objects of their environment.

Moreover, individuals' adequacy impacts their office since their convictions about their self-efficacy can shape and guide their decisions, endeavors, commitment, and even mindsets (Henson, 2001). Moreover, Gallagher (2012) stated that self-efficacy is important to social cognitive theory, determination, and innovative thinking. Self-efficacy beliefs influence how people think, behave, and encourage themselves. (Bourne et. al., 2021; Bandura, 1994).

According to social cognitive theory, perceived self-efficacy influences attitudes that sustain consistency in the attitude-behavior link (Yoong et al., 2018; Moore & Homer, 2008; Glasman & Albarracn, 2006). According to Yoong et al. (2018), self-efficacy can relieve mental stress and improve people's attitudes toward behavior. Thus, self-efficacy might be seen as having an important influence on attitudes.

Moreover, Bandura (1977) stated that individuals develop their self-efficacy beliefs by synthesizing information from four key sources of influence. These encompass mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and personal emotional and physiological states. Individuals utilize these sources to evaluate their strengths and capabilities (Bhati & Tejaswini, 2022).

The sources of influence were explained by Bandura (1977) and, as cited by Macafee and Comeau (2020). The mastery experiences have the biggest impact on self-efficacy. It represents one's perception of the success or failure of prior

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experiences. Repeated success can foster strong efficacy expectations, minimizing the harm caused by sporadic failures. On the other hand, observing the behaviors of others provides vicarious experience information. Observing others accomplish jobs without negative repercussions can reinforce one's notion that they can perform similar things successfully.

Nonetheless, vicarious experience, which relies on inferences drawn from social comparison, is deemed less reliable and more susceptible to change compared to mastery experiences. Moreover, the process of influencing someone verbally involves receiving input from other people. Efficacy expectations can be raised or lowered in response to both positive and negative comments. When people participate in settings that favor effective performance, verbal feedback can convince them they can handle difficult problems, even when their efficacy beliefs are lower than those based on personal experiences. Lastly, physiological and affective states describe the physical and emotional responses that influence how one perceives one's level of competence. People partly evaluate their susceptibility to stress based on their physiological arousal level. People are less likely to predict success when feeling tense and nervous because high arousal frequently hampers performance.

In relation to this, the current study aims to examine the association between self-efficacy and attitude. Thus, the person conducting the study anticipated that self-efficacy would be linked to attitudes and the profile variables.

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

This study revolves around three (3) variables: (1) self-efficacy, (2) attitude, and (3) profile or demographic variables. Self-efficacy is concerned with people's confidence in their aptitudes. Albert Bandura (1977) outlines that individuals shape their self-efficacy beliefs through information processing from four primary sources of influence: mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and individual emotional and physiological states. These sources serve as tools for individuals to evaluate their strengths and capabilities (Bhati & Tejaswini, 2022). In this study, the four sources of influence are included. Mastery experience refers to how students do well on their specialized subject assignments. Vicarious experience refers to how the learners do well in

HUMSS-specialized subjects. Social persuasion refers to how the learners are praised for their ability in HUMSS-specialized subjects. Lastly, emotional and physiological states refer to how students get anxious about the HUMSS-specialized subject.

On the other side, attitude refers to the way of thinking and emotions that determine how someone acts and conceptualizes (Shih et al., 2010). In this study, attitude refers to students' propensity to react favorably or unfavorably to their specialized Humanities and Social Sciences subjects.

The respondents' demographics are based on sex, birth order, and monthly income of their families. Sex refers to the state of being male or female. It is the biological differences between males and females (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2019). Birth order describes the sequence in which children are born in a family, such as firstborn and second-born (Sam, 2023). Family Monthly Income, as defined in this study, refers to the total monthly income received by all members of a family before taxes. Specifically, in the context of this research, it denotes the monthly salary earned by the families of the respondents (Family Income - Health, United States, 2022).

This study aims to identify and describe the SHS learners' levels of self-efficacy and attitudes about the HUMSS Strand's specialized subjects and determine the relationship between self-efficacy and attitude when grouped according to the demographic profile variables. The researcher considered the study relevant since the data can be used to enhance or implement intervention programs to improve the self-efficacy and attitude level of SHS students in their HUMSS specialized subjects. It will also assist the teacher in improving the teaching and learning process inside the classroom. The study will also serve as the foundation for future research involving all upcoming grade 11 and 12 students enrolled in the Humanities and Social Sciences Strand or other strand offering specialized subjects in HUMSS.

Based on the stated concepts above, this study is patterned after the Paradigm below to illustrate the relationships between the variables, sub-variables, and the research process of the study. This paradigm serves as the schematic diagram of the investigation.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Figure 1 shows the flow of the study. The first box provides the study's demographic profile variables, such as sex, birth order, and monthly income for the family. The upper box on the right represents self-efficacy, with the four sources of influence in self-efficacy: mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and individual emotional and physiological states. Students' attitude toward HUMSS-specialized subjects is shown in the lower box on the right. The arrow linking the boxes on the right demonstrates the significant relationship between self-efficacy and students' attitudes about specialized subjects in HUMSS. The arrow connecting the boxes on the left and right depicts the significant relationship between self-efficacy and attitudes of the SHS learners when grouped according to the demographic profile variables. The arrow pointing towards the box below the clustered profile variables, self-efficacy, and attitude illustrates how the enhancement program will be designed based on the study's findings to improve students' self-efficacy and attitude.

Self-efficacy is defined as individuals' belief in their capacity to successfully perform a task or achieve a goal based on their confidence in possessing the requisite skills (Bandura, 1977). It was categorized into four categories: mastery of experience, social support, emotional status, and vicarious experiences. On the other hand, attitude is characterized as the relatively stable arrangement of beliefs, emotions, and behavioral inclinations towards socially significant entities, groups, occurrences, or symbols. (Hogg & Vaughan, 2005), The outcome of the study is a learning enhancement program to supplement the needs of the learners in the specialized subjects of the Humanities and Social Sciences strand.

Statement of the Problem

The study determined the influence of self-efficacy on the attitude of SHS learners in their Specialized subjects in Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) at Tuao High School during the School Year 2023-2024.

Specifically, this research sought answers to the following:

1. What is the learners' self-efficacy level in general according to mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and emotional and physiological states of individuals?
2. What is the learners' attitude level on the specialized subjects?
3. Is there a significant difference between self-efficacy level and attitude level when grouped according to the profile variables?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of self-efficacy and attitude level?
5. What learning enhancement program can be crafted to enhance the self-efficacy and attitude level of SHS learners toward their specialized subjects in Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS)?

Statement of Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between self-efficacy level and attitude level when grouped according to the profile variables; and,
2. There is no significant relationship between respondents' self-efficacy and their attitude on specialized subjects.

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the embedded mixed-methods design. This design involves prioritizing one research method within a particular setting while incorporating another method to complement and enrich its findings (Creswell, 2008; cited by Kimmons, 2022). The quantitative designs used were descriptive, comparative, and correlational designs. A descriptive research design is employed to collect data to develop precise predictions about a certain issue or hypothesis (Qualtrics, 2023). In this study, a descriptive design was used to interpret the data on the demographic profile, self-efficacy, and attitude toward the respondents' specialized subjects.

On the other hand, comparative design is about looking at an object of study to another. The object of study is normally compared across space and time (Weltzien et al., 2022). This study used the comparative design to determine the differences in the student respondents' self-efficacy and attitude when grouped according to their profile variables. Lastly, the correlational research design is used when the researcher employs correlational statistics to gauge and depict the extent of association among variables or scores (Creswell, 2012, cited by Hayyi, 2014). This study used the correlational design to ascertain the connection between respondents' attitudes and self-efficacy. In addition, the quantitative data were embedded with qualitative data gathered through interviews of a cohort of 15 students. The embedded design employed in this study involved the concurrent collection and integration of quantitative data via surveys and qualitative data through interviews. This methodological approach was intended to achieve a thorough exploration of senior high school students' self-efficacy and attitudes toward HUMSS-specialized subjects at Tuao High School. Utilizing both numerical measurements and in-depth narratives offered a comprehensive perspective on the factors influencing students' experiences and perceptions within their educational environment. The integration of these datasets enabled the researcher to uncover insights that might be less discernible if either approach were employed independently, thereby contributing to a more nuanced understanding of student self-efficacy and attitudes in an academic context.

Research Environment

This study was conducted during the Second Quarter of the School Year 2023-2024 at Tuao High School. It is located in Meña St. Tuao South, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya.

Tuao High School is the lone Secondary School of the Bagabag II of the Schools Division of Nueva Vizcaya. Its history is based on the concept of Dr. Pedro Orata, the father of Barangay High Schools in the province of Nueva Vizcaya and the proponent of community high schools. It was created in response to the "community school" concept, which was originally built in the Singian Hills, west of Barangay Tuao. It was previously known as Tuao Barangay High School before being renamed Tuao Community Pilot Public High School (TCPHPS). When TCPHPS relocated to the Tuao Elementary School site in 1967, it became known as the NVSIT Tuao Campus after it became one of the NVSIT's campuses and relocated to an 80-hectare plot of property held by the NVSIT in 1975. In the year 2000, all NVSIT and NVSPC satellite schools were handed over to DECS. So, classes were temporarily housed in empty classrooms in the elementary school from 2000 to 2001. In the following year, all classes were moved to Tuao Elementary School. Only in August 2003 did Tuao High School get a permanent home.

At present, Tuao High School is offering the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand with specialized subjects, namely, Philippine Politics and Governance (PPG), Disciplines and Ideas in the Social Sciences (DISS), Creative Writing (CW), Creative Nonfiction (CNF), Disciplines and Ideas in the Applied Social Sciences.

Tuao High School's recent implementation of the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) Strand signifies a deliberate shift from the General Academic Strand (GAS) in its Senior High School curriculum. This strategic adjustment is aimed at providing specialized subjects tailored to meet the specific academic interests and career aspirations of its student body. Emphasizing the importance of ongoing development, the School Head highlights the necessity to continuously broaden and refine the scope of HUMSS subjects to cater to the needs of enrolled students effectively.

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Figure 2. Research Locale Map

Research Respondents

The research instruments were administered to the SHS students of Tuao High School during the School Year 2023-2024. With a language teacher's support, the researcher collected data from 32 Grade 11 learners and 50 Grade 12 learners, all of whom were selected through a population study. However, participation was hindered for some learners who were currently enrolled in modular learning due to health-related issues. The research population or target population encompassed all individuals, objects, or events sharing particular characteristics that were of interest to the researcher. Researchers typically prioritized data collection from smaller or readily accessible populations, especially those with distinctive or crucial traits (Thomas, 2023).

Table 1. Respondents' Section

Section	n
11 – Einstein	32
12 – Aristotle	25
12- Newton	25
Total (N)	82

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the demographic profile of the 82 respondents in terms of sex, birth order, and family monthly income.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile Variables		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	45	54.9%
	Female	37	45.1%
Birth Order	First Born Sibling	30	36.6%
	Middle Born Sibling	42	51.2%
	Youngest Born Sibling	10	12.2%
Family Monthly Income	43,828 & above	10	12.2%
	21,194 - 43,827	12	14.6%
	10,957 - 21,193	20	24.4%
	Below 10,957	40	48.8%

Table 2 presents that out of 82 respondents, 45 (54.9%) were male, while 37 (45.1%) of the respondents were female. This implies that there were more males than females in this study. In terms of birth order, the Table reveals that the majority of the respondents were middle-born siblings (n=42, 51.2%) followed by first-born siblings (n=30, 36.6%), while the least were the youngest-born siblings (10,12.2%).

Finally, by family monthly income, 40 (48.8%) respondents had a monthly income of below Php 10,957. In

comparison, 20 (24.4%) earned a monthly income of Php 10,957 to Php 21,193, and 12 (14.6%) earned a monthly income of Php 21,184 to Php 43,827. The remaining 10 (12.2%) respondents earned 43,828 & above. It infers that the majority of the respondents were classified as poor.

Research Instruments

The researcher administered a survey questionnaire with the help of language teachers in Grades

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11 and 12 learners who were eligible respondents for this study. The questionnaire that was utilized was adopted and modified to investigate the association between HUMSS learners' self-efficacy and attitude toward specialized subjects to the Profile Variables Sex (Male and Female), Birth Order (First, Middle, and Youngest), and Family Monthly Income. It underwent reliability analysis by a duly accredited quantitative data analyst at the University Research Center of Saint Mary's University.

The survey questionnaire that was administered was composed of three parts. Part I of the survey questionnaire was utilized to gather personal information on the respondents, including sex, birth, and monthly income of the family. Part II was composed of 13 questions adapted from Peura et al. (2021) to determine the learners' self-efficacy level in general according to mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and emotional and physiological states of individuals. It underwent a pilot testing and reliability test, acquiring a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.700. Lastly, Part III was composed of questions assessing the attitude level of the students on the specialized subjects adapted from Fennema-Sherman Attitude Scales (Fennema & Sherman, 1976) that were used in the studies of Kahveci (2010). The FSMAS instrument was highly reliable, with a Cronbach-alpha of 0.777.

The instrument was also used in the study of Dantzler et al. (2014), where the overall internal consistency estimate using Cronbach's alpha was .77, indicating strong reliability. Similarly, Ren et al. (2016) found that the revised FSMAS could reliably measure lower-primary teachers' mathematical attitudes, suggesting its usefulness for evaluating professional development programs. Takunyaci et al. (2019) examined the Turkish translation's construct validity through exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis and reliability via item analysis, Cronbach's Alpha, and split-half correlation. The adaptation resulted in a valid and reliable scale suitable for Turkish cultures.

A pilot test and reliability test were also conducted by the researcher with 30 Senior High School students at Murong National High School. The result on the Self-Efficacy was acceptable since the computed Cronbach Alpha is 0.707. Likewise, the result on the Attitude was acceptable based on the computed Cronbach's Alpha of 0.700. These signify that the research instrument used for final testing is reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured a letter to the Principal of Murong National High School to conduct a pilot test. After the letter was signed and approved by the designated personnel, the researcher personally administered the pilot testing. Before giving the instrument to the respondents, the

researcher gave a brief explanation of its intents and contents and informed them that all information acquired, including their identities, would be kept confidential and hidden. The names had been coded as an alternative. In addition, the researcher clarified that there were three parts: the profile of the respondents, the self-efficacy, and the attitude toward the specialized subjects of the HUMSS strand. The researcher was instructed to finish the survey in 15 minutes. The timer started upon reaching all the students' tables, and the researcher collected the instrument after 15 minutes. The researcher kept the data gathered until the research paper was finished. In terms of disposal, the survey and questionnaires were not discarded. Still, they were kept secure by the researcher or scanned and saved on a flash drive to which only the researcher had access.

Along with the ethical concerns in data gathering, for final testing, the study underwent the following procedures to get the needed data:

Spanning several months, the procedure involved a series of strategic tasks and interactions to ensure robust data collection, rigorous analysis, and scholarly interpretation. Since it was given 12 months validity by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB), Commencing on February 8, 2024, the process unfolded with the drafting of a request letter to the Schools Division Superintendent and a transmittal letter to the Tuao High School Principal requesting approval for the study's conduct and data collection. This initial step underlined the importance of ethical collaboration and endorsement in the research process.

Subsequently, in the same month, meticulous planning took place to ensure the effective floating and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher orchestrated a precise schedule for the distribution of the questionnaire to the identified respondents. When approved, the researcher went to the Grade 11 and 12 Advisers and requested the total population of students currently enrolled in this School Year 2023-2024 and their names per section. Following that, the researcher has provided the Informed Consent Form to the respondents and their parents for those who are under the age of 18 or are classified as a "child" under RA 9344. This was done on February 20, 2024.

After identifying the total population, the researcher sought assistance from language teachers to streamline the data collection process. The researcher provided a briefing on the procedures, and questionnaires were distributed during face-to-face classes, utilizing students' vacant periods for implementation. The administration of data gathering was done on March 22, 2024.

After gathering the pertinent data, statistical treatment and analysis were done. The analysis and interpretation phase was seamlessly extended to April,

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where the researcher delved deeper into the data findings. This process involved critical reflection and insightful deduction, ensuring the study's results were accurate and

meaningfully interpreted in the broader context of Social Studies Education.

Table 3. Timeline for the Completion of Each Phase of the Study

Stage	Activity	Date	Deliverable
Pilot Testing	Conduct a Pilot Test of the Research Questionnaire	November 14, 2023	Pilot Tested Questionnaires
Data Collection	Drafting of Request letter	February 8, 2024	I signed a request letter from the Schools Division Superintendent of Nueva Vizcaya and the school principal of Tuao High School.
	Carry out data collection.	March 22, 2024	Raw Data
	Write up data collection.	March 23, 2024	Draft data collection
Analysis	Prepare data for analysis	March 24-25, 2024	Data Ready for Analysis
	Analyze data	March 26-April 8, 2024	Notes and other output from the Analysis
	Draw conclusions/ recommendations.	April 9-10, 2024	Draft Data Analysis and Finding section final report
Writing up	The final draft of the application	June 10, 2024	Final Draft
	Final defense	June 24, 2024	Notes of Feedback
	Final Editing	June 25-July 20, 2024	Integrate Feedback and recommendations
	Submission	July 31, 2024	Final Submission of Paper

Treatment of Data

1. Descriptive statistics like mean and standard deviation were used to describe self-efficacy. The following scale was used:

Table 4. Interpretation of Likert Scale for Assessing Self-Efficacy

Scale	Response	Qualitative Description
1.0-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Very low Self-efficacy
1.50-2.49	Disagree	Low Self-efficacy
2.50-3.49	Agree	High Self-efficacy
3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Self-efficacy

2. To determine the attitude level of the respondents, mean and standard deviations were used, the following scale was used:

Table 5. Likert Scale Interpretation to Determine the Attitude Level of the Respondents

Scale	Response	Qualitative Description
1.0-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Favorable to a very little extent
1.50-2.49	Disagree	Favorable to a little extent
2.50-3.49	Agree	Favorable to a moderate extent
3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree	Favorable to a great extent

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3. To determine the significant relationship between the respondents' self-efficacy level and attitude level, the parametric (Pearson r) statistical tool was used.

4. The nonparametric (Kruskal Wallis, Mann-Whitney U Test) statistical tool was used in determining the significant difference between self-efficacy and attitude when grouped according to profile variables.

Ethical Considerations

As much as the study deals immensely with human participation, specifically dealing with their perceptions and experiences on how their Self-efficacy and attitudes implicate the Specialized subjects in HUMSS, this study considered ethical consideration.

The study was submitted for ethics review to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) with address and contact information at SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos, Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. The SMU REB is headed by Mr. Jayson Arnold L. Maslang, who can be reached via email (jmaslang@smu.edu.ph) and mobile number-09178787967).

Conflict of Interest

The researcher is a teacher in the research locale, and the respondents are her students, which possessed a potential conflict of interest. The researcher ensured that the respondents' vulnerability was not exploited by explaining to them the significance and purpose of the study. Respondent participation in the study was purely voluntary. It was made clear that their involvement or non-involvement would not have any impact on their grading schemes. With the principal's approval, the researcher asked the language teachers for assistance in distributing questionnaires to the participants.

Privacy, Confidentiality, and Data Protection

The researcher assured the respondents that all information obtained, including their names, is kept anonymous and hidden. As an alternative, the names have been coded. The researcher must keep the data acquired until the manuscript is completed. Regarding disposal, the survey and questionnaires must not be discarded. Still, they must be maintained in safekeeping by the researcher or scanned and stored on a flash drive that only the researcher has access to.

Management of Vulnerability

The vulnerability may occur in terms of identity, which has been treated with great anonymity, as indicated in the preceding sections of the study. When the participants

felt any discomfort or inconvenience, they were given the chance to withdraw from answering the questionnaire.

Another occurrence of vulnerability could be in the hands of the researcher and enumerators. These were avoided, and respondents' sensitivity was reduced by describing and explaining all aspects of the study and questionnaire in such a way and in a language that the respondents could understand with the help of the language teacher. Participants' assent has been obtained through voluntary means, ensuring they freely agree to participate. They have comprehended the research's nature and requirements, and individuals affected have been competent to consent. This signifies that participants have been thoroughly informed about the study, understood the information provided, and possessed the capacity to decide whether or not to take part.

Risk/Benefit Ratio

There are no risks associated with this study. It has not been used as a basis for additional or deductions in the learners' grading systems. Considering identification as a risk, it has been managed appropriately by issuing codes and storing the necessary files.

The benefits truly outweigh the harm of this study. However, the outcomes have not directly benefitted the parents or students; this had benefitted the larger public by providing recommendations and programs that could be adopted by the Schools in the Division of Nueva Vizcaya, particularly the schools offering specialized subjects in HUMSS strand in the Senior High School.

Informed Consent

The researcher reaffirmed that an informed consent form is used to obtain the respondents' consent in the survey and interview. The researcher made sure that the respondents were informed through the help of the language teachers before completing the informed permission form and highlighted that the data would only be used for educational purposes. The language teachers also provided clear instructions on how respondents should approach and answer the questions, ensuring clarity and coherence in their responses. They also informed them that it would require approximately 10 to 15 minutes to complete, allowing respondents to allocate their time effectively during the process. Additionally, the respondents have not been enticed to participate in the process by the promise of financial reward. The researcher disclaims that if answering the questions causes participants any distress or harm, they may stop or indicate their intention not to participate.

Furthermore, before conducting semi-structured interviews, respondents were contacted via messenger to request their consent through a formal letter formally. They

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were briefed on the interview process and informed that it typically takes 25-30 minutes. In addition, they received the interview questions in advance to familiarize themselves with the topics and prepare initial responses, facilitating a smoother and more efficient discussion during the interview. This approach aims to optimize time management and improve the quality of information gathered.

Terms of Reference

Since the researcher conducted the study in Tuao High School, where she is teaching and is currently a student at Saint Mary's University, the output shall be owned by Tuao High School, Saint Mary's University, and the researcher as author.

Dissemination Plan

The dissemination plan for the study employs diverse strategies to maximize impact. Research findings will be published in peer-reviewed journals focused on educational and social sciences. Presentations will be delivered at key conferences like the General Assembly Meeting, targeting educators, stakeholders, administrators, and researchers. Webinars will broaden outreach, and findings will be summarized for dissemination through educational websites. Collaboration with local education authorities and schools will facilitate workshops and seminars to discuss practical implications. Feedback mechanisms, including surveys, will assess the effectiveness of dissemination efforts, ensuring continuous improvement to enhance the study's influence on educational practices and policy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1. Level of Self-Efficacy towards the Specialized Subjects of HUMSS Strand

Table 6. Level of Self-Efficacy of the Respondents towards the Specialized HUMSS Strand Subjects

Items	M	SD	QD
Mastery of Experience			
1. I have always been successful with HUMSS-specialized subjects.	2.96	.867	H
2. I do well on my specialized subject assignments.	2.93	.539	H
3. I do well on even the most difficult specialized subjects' assignments.	2.82	.547	H
Overall Mean	2.90	.469	H
Social Persuasion			
1. My teachers have told me I am good at learning the HUMSS specialized subjects.	2.65	.692	H
2. Adults in my family have told me what a good HUMSS student I am.	2.49	.805	L
3. I have been praised for my ability in HUMSS-specialized subjects.	2.61	.698	H
4. Other students have told me that I'm good at learning HUMSS-specialized subjects	2.54	.757	H
Overall Mean	2.57	.599	H
Vicarious Experience			
1. Seeing students do better than me in the specialized subjects pushes me to do better	3.09	.632	H
2. I imagine myself being good in humanities and social sciences.	3.02	.753	H
3. I admire adults who are good in humanities and social sciences.	3.07	.750	H
Overall Mean	3.06	.542	H
Physiological and Emotional States			
1. I get anxious when I know that I have to read aloud during my specialized subjects class.	2.56	.722	H
2. I start to feel anxious as soon as I begin working on my specialized subjects.	2.55	.632	H
3. I feel tension in my body when I have to do HUMSS-specialized subjects.	2.57	.648	H
Overall Mean	2.63	.311	H
Grand Mean	2.77	3.60	H

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Very High Self Efficacy (VH); 2.50 – 3.49 High Self Efficacy (H); 1.50 – 2.49 Low Self Efficacy (L); 1.00 – 1.49 Very Low Self Efficacy (VL)

Table 6 presents the respondents' self-efficacy level towards the specialized subjects in the HUMSS Strand. Concerning mastery of experience, the total mean is 2.90 (SD = .469), which is qualitatively described as "high self-efficacy." It indicates that the respondents have great confidence in their ability to succeed in learning tasks, which in turn can lead to higher achievement and satisfaction with

the learning process. Table 6 also reveals that the students have always been successful (M= 2.96, SD=.867) and do well on the assignments (M=2.93, SD =.539), even the most difficult assignments on their specialized subjects (M=2.82, SD=.547). Results showed that practice is undeniably one of the most effective methods for learning new skills and enhancing performance in any activity (Garrido, 2023).

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In addition, the responses from the interview reveal a wide range of self-efficacy levels among students toward HUMSS specialized subjects. Under mastery of experience, their insights offer valuable perspectives on students' self-efficacy in understanding the subject matter, achieving success in assignments, and developing critical thinking skills—all of which play crucial roles in shaping their overall confidence levels.

Firstly, there is a clear connection between comprehension and confidence. Students frequently noted that their confidence in handling assignments improved as their understanding of the subject matter deepened. For instance, one student reflected, “In my experiences with HUMSS-specialized subjects, I gained some confidence in doing my activities and assignments because I gradually learned by understanding what the teacher taught.” Another student elaborated on this, saying, “HUMSS-specialized subjects tend to make me feel confident in my ability to handle activities and assignments. I have likely developed an understanding of the subject matter, which helps me approach challenging assignments with a sense of familiarity. For example, when our teacher in DISS gave us the task to make a list of arguments for our debate, critical analysis helped me to navigate primary sources efficiently, allowing me to craft well-argued arguments and meet the assignment demands with confidence.”

Interest in specific HUMSS subjects also correlates strongly with higher levels of confidence. One student mentioned, “One of my favorite subjects is under HUMSS, and that’s why my self-confidence is high towards the subject.” This highlights the motivational impact of personal preference on self-efficacy. Additionally, success in assignments and positive feedback play a crucial role in reinforcing students' confidence. As one student stated, “I feel quite confident in my ability to learn and excel in HUMSS-specialized subjects due to my critical thinking, analysis, and writing skills. For instance, my success in my senior high school journey, especially in Social Sciences, where I consistently receive high grades and positive feedback, reinforces my confidence.” Another student echoed this sentiment, noting the impact of positive feedback on their self-efficacy.

There is, however, notable variability in confidence levels among students. Some exhibit consistent confidence, as illustrated by responses such as “I am quite confident” and “Yes, I am quite confident.” Conversely, others experience fluctuations in their confidence, which can depend on the difficulty of the topic or personal reservations. For example, one student expressed, “*Medyo lang*” (Somewhat), while another noted, “I think yes but not so confident.”

Cultural and linguistic diversity further enriches the understanding of self-efficacy. One student articulated how their experiences with HUMSS subjects have significantly

influenced their confidence, especially with challenging lessons, saying, “*Ang mga karanasan ko sa mga specialized-subjects ko ng HUMSS ay malaki ang impluwensya sa aking kumpiyansa sa paggawa ng mga aralin at takdang-aralin, lalo na sa mga mahirap na lesson*” (My experiences with specialized HUMSS subjects significantly influence my confidence in handling lessons and assignments, especially with challenging topics).

Overall, these responses highlight the intricate interplay of understanding, interest, achievement, and personal perception in shaping students' self-efficacy toward specialized HUMSS subjects. Understanding these dynamics can aid educators in creating a supportive learning environment that enhances student confidence and engagement across diverse academic contexts.

In terms of social persuasion, the overall mean is 2.57 (SD = .599), which is qualitatively described as “high self-efficacy.” It indicates that the respondents will likely approach persuasive situations confidently and effectively, leading to positive outcomes in their personal and professional interactions. The table also reveals that the students have been told how good they are at learning HUMSS specialized subjects by the teachers (M=2.65, SD=.692) and peers (M=2.54, SD=.757). Even themselves praised their abilities in HUMSS specialized subjects (M=2.61, SD=.698). On the other hand, the adult members of their families did not do the same (M=2.49, SD=.805). This mirrors the findings of Zakariya's study (2022), which suggests that timely encouragement from teachers, parents, peers, and other competent adults can enhance students' confidence in navigating challenging situations.

Moreover, the interview responses provide insightful perspectives on the role of social persuasion in shaping students' self-efficacy toward HUMSS-specialized subjects. Social persuasion, as described by Bandura (1977) and further explored by Veerman and Duchatelet (2024), refers to the influence of others' feedback, encouragement, and praise on individuals' beliefs about their capabilities. Social persuasion, which includes encouragement and positive feedback from teachers, family, and peers, plays a crucial role in shaping students' confidence and motivation. Many students stated that praise from teachers lightens their mood and boosts their confidence. For instance, one student noted, “The praise from my teachers also lightens my mood and boosts my confidence.” However, they also mentioned that negative comments from family can diminish this enthusiasm. This highlights the nuanced effect of social persuasion, where positive reinforcement from some sources can be countered by negative feedback from others. Similarly, students expressed that positive affirmations significantly influence their perception of their abilities, with one stating, “Yes, positive affirmations do influence my perception of my abilities in HUMSS-specialized subjects.”

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The interest and engagement of teachers were also frequently mentioned as crucial factors in enhancing motivation and performance. Students observed that when teachers show genuine interest, it positively affects their motivation and engagement, as evidenced by comments such as, “The interest of the teachers affects my motivation and engagement with the specialized subjects.” This sentiment is further supported by another student who noted, “*Ang interes na ipinapakita ng aking mga guro ay malaking bahagi ng aking pag-unlad sa mga espesyal na asignatura ng HUMSS. Ang kanilang pagtutok at suporta ay nagbibigay sa akin ng inspirasyon at nagpapalakas ng aking loob na makakaya ko ang mga hamon*” (The interest shown by my teachers is a significant part of my development in HUMSS subjects. Their attention and support inspire me and strengthen my belief that I can overcome challenges). This aligns with educational research highlighting the importance of teacher encouragement and support in fostering students' academic self-efficacy (Bapst et al., 2022; Pajares, 1996).

Additionally, the impact of positive interactions extends beyond immediate confidence boosts to long-term motivational benefits. For instance, students indicated that such interactions help reinforce their knowledge and skills, making them feel more capable of handling complex ideas and challenging assignments. One student elaborated, “This positive interaction has helped me to boost my confidence and self-esteem; it reinforces my knowledge and skills in HUMSS-specialized subjects, making me feel more capable of handling challenges, especially in understanding complex ideas.” Furthermore, acknowledgment from teachers, family, and friends motivates students to perform better and continue improving, as illustrated by responses such as, “When teachers, family, and friends say I'm doing well, it makes me feel like I can do even better,” and “*Gusto ko pa lalong pagbutihin dahil naappreciate nila ako*” (I want to improve further because they appreciate me).

Overall, these responses underscore the significant role that social persuasion plays in enhancing students' self-efficacy, suggesting that consistent, positive reinforcement from key figures is instrumental in boosting confidence and motivation in academic contexts.

The total overall mean with regard to vicarious experience is 3.06 (SD = .541), which is qualitatively described as “high self-efficacy.” It indicates that the respondents have a strong belief in their ability to succeed based on the successful experiences of others. The table also reveals that the students are motivated to do better if they see students doing better than them (M=3.09, SD=.632). They admire adults who are good in humanities and social sciences (M=3.07, SD=.750), and they also imagine that they are good in humanities and social sciences (M=3.02, SD=.753). Results showed that one boosts their confidence in

their ability to do the same when someone else accomplishes a task or overcomes a challenge (Giardina, 2022).

Furthermore, the interview responses shed light on how vicarious experiences influence students' self-efficacy in specialized HUMSS subjects. Vicarious experience, a concept central to Bandura's social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1986), refers to learning from observing others' successes and failures. Several themes emerge from the responses that illustrate this phenomenon.

Many students indicated that seeing their peers excel in HUMSS-specialized subjects serves as a powerful motivator. For instance, one student noted, “Everything I learn in these specialized subjects motivates me even more because they further open my mind to the necessity of understanding them deeply.” At the same time, another mentioned, “Comparing with higher-performing peers in specialized subjects can be a powerful motivator.” This response highlights that observing the success of high-achieving peers creates a desire to improve and reach similar levels of proficiency, inspiring students to work harder and strive for excellence. The concept of envisioning success and setting clear goals, as noted in another response, “Envisioning success in the humanities and social sciences can help me set clear goals and maintain focus,” illustrates how imagining oneself achieving success helps maintain motivation and direction.

Furthermore, admiration for proficient adults and their methods can also serve as a source of motivation. As one student shared, “Observing how they approach their work and overcome challenges can provide valuable insights and methodologies for my learning journey.” This shows that students are influenced not only by their peers but also by successful role models whose strategies and accomplishments provide practical guidance and inspiration.

However, the impact of these vicarious experiences varies among students. Some students feel strongly motivated when comparing themselves to high-performing peers, as evidenced by responses such as, “It motivates me whenever I compare myself to those who are higher-performing peers because I've realized that I should work harder and improve.” This aligns with Bandura's assertion that observing others' achievements can heighten one's belief in their capabilities (Bandura, 1982). Moreover, comparing oneself with proficient peers can instill a desire to improve and adopt effective learning strategies.

In contrast, others report a more modest effect, with responses like, “*Minsan po pero hindi naman gaano*” (Sometimes, but not very much) and “*Hindi naman gaano okey lang sa akin kasi hindi naman ako ganun kagaling*” (It doesn't affect me much because I don't consider myself that good). This variability suggests that while vicarious experiences can be motivating, their impact is also contingent on individual perceptions and confidence levels.

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Overall, the responses reveal that observing the achievements of peers and role models can significantly influence students' self-efficacy by providing motivation, inspiration, and practical strategies for improvement. While most students are motivated by high-performing peers and successful role models, the extent of this motivation can vary, reflecting individual differences in how vicarious experiences are perceived and utilized.

Table 6 also presents the level of self-efficacy of the respondents in terms of physiological and emotional states. It shows that self-efficacy under physiological and emotional states has an overall mean of 2.63 (SD = .311), which is qualitatively described as "high self-efficacy." It indicates that the respondents can handle stress and challenges effectively, leading to better outcomes in various areas of life. The table also reveals that the students feel tension in their bodies when they have to do HUMSS-specialized subjects (M=2.57, SD=.648). They get anxious when they read aloud inside the class (2.56, SD=.722). As soon as they begin to do work on specialized subjects (M=2.55, SD=.632), Positive physiological and emotional states in the context of self-efficacy reflect a combination of heightened physical well-being and positive emotions, accompanied by a strong belief in one's ability to accomplish tasks and achieve goals. This state of readiness and confidence can enhance motivation, performance, and overall success in various endeavors (Ackerman, 2018).

In addition, the interview responses highlight the influence of physiological and emotional states on students' self-efficacy in specialized HUMSS subjects. Physiological and emotional factors, as discussed in Bandura's social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1997), play a significant role in shaping individuals' beliefs about their capabilities.

Their responses show a significant relationship between feelings of apprehension and performance. Students frequently reported that nervousness and tenseness affect their ability to concentrate, which in turn impacts their engagement and performance in academic tasks.

Many students described how tension can diminish their focus and motivation. For example, one student explained, "When I feel tense during an activity, I find it difficult to focus on what I'm doing, and I lose my motivation to participate." This sentiment is echoed by others who noted that unease can lead to decreased comprehension and overall performance. Another student remarked, "When I feel uneasy or apprehensive, it can affect my concentration, making it more difficult for me to engage with the lessons we are

studying fully." This aligns with research indicating that emotional states can impact cognitive processes and academic performance (Pekrun et al., 2012).

While some students experience significant challenges due to apprehension, such as feeling embarrassed when performing in front of others or encountering mental blocks, others have developed strategies to manage these emotions. One student shared, "Feeling uneasy can sometimes make it harder for me to read aloud or focus on assigned tasks in these subjects. However, I've learned that preparing well and knowing mindfulness exercises can help me feel more comfortable." This indicates that, despite the negative impact of tension, students who employ coping strategies like preparation and mindfulness may better manage their emotional states and mitigate their effects on performance.

Responses also highlighted a range of individual experiences with apprehension. For instance, some students reported that nervousness does not significantly affect their performance, with statements such as, "Just feeling nervous, but it doesn't affect your performance in doing the activity." Conversely, others struggle more noticeably, with comments like, "Siyempre po ah kasi nemental block ako kapag kinakabahan ako" (Of course, because I experience mental blocks when I am anxious), and, "Nakaka mental block, hindi na alam ang isasagot" (It causes mental blocks; I no longer know what to answer).

Overall, these responses underscore the complex role of physiological and emotional states in influencing students' self-efficacy. Apprehension and nervousness can impair focus and performance, but effective coping strategies and preparation can help mitigate these effects. The variability in individual experiences highlights the importance of addressing emotional and physiological factors to support students' academic engagement and success in HUMSS subjects.

Lastly, Table 6 presents the rating of the different indicators of self-efficacy and the overall rating. The table indicates that the computed overall rating is 2.77 (SD=.360), which is qualitatively described as "high self-efficacy." It also reveals that the four key factors of self-efficacy have been responded to satisfactorily, which indicates that learners have a high self-efficacy towards the specialized subjects in Humanities and Social Sciences. The result shows that respondents are more determined than content with what they are receiving, according to the study of Gaumer and Noonan (2021).

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Section 2. Level of Attitude towards the specialized subjects of HUMSS strand

Table 7. Level of Attitude on the Specialized Subjects

Attitude	M	SD	QD
1. I am sure that I can learn HUMSS specialized subjects.	3.35	.616	ME
2. My teachers have been interested in my progress in HUMSS-specialized subjects.	2.91	.740	ME
3. Knowing concepts in HUMSS specialized subjects will help me earn a living.	3.22	.545	ME
4. I don't think I could do advanced HUMSS specialized subjects.	2.50	.689	ME
5. HUMSS-specialized subjects will not be important to me in my life's work.	1.90	.883	LE
6. Getting a teacher to take me seriously in the HUMSS specialized subjects is a problem.	2.21	.885	LE
7. HUMSS specialized subject is hard for me.	2.37	.712	LE
8. I'll need Humanities and Social Sciences for my future work.	3.40	.735	ME
9. I am sure of myself when I do activities about HUMSS specialized subjects.	2.95	.627	ME
10. I don't expect to use HUMSS-specialized subjects when I get out of school.	2.32	.664	LE
11. It's hard to get HUMSS specialized subject teachers to respect me.	2.40	.718	LE
12. HUMSS specialized subjects are worthwhile, necessary subjects.	2.82	.687	ME
13. Taking a HUMSS-specialized subject is a waste of time.	1.85	.877	LE
14. HUMSS specialized subjects have been my worst subject.	1.95	.845	LE
15. I think I could handle more difficult activities in HUMSS-specialized subjects.	2.72	.653	ME
16. I will use the concept of Humanities and Social Sciences in many ways as an adult.	3.18	.650	ME
17. I see Humanities and Social Sciences as something I won't use very often when I get out of high school.	2.39	.766	LE
18. I feel that specialized teachers in HUMSS ignore me when I try to talk about something serious.	2.18	.918	LE
19. I can get good grades in HUMSS specialized subjects.	2.79	.643	ME
20. I 'll need a good understanding of humanities and social sciences for my future work.	3.13	.750	ME
21. I know I can do well in HUMSS-specialized subjects.	3.12	.710	ME
22. Doing well in HUMSS specialized subjects is not important for my future.	2.07	1.040	LE
23. My teachers would not take me seriously if I told them I was interested in a career in humanities and social sciences.	2.22	.889	LE
24. I am sure I could do advanced work in HUMSS-specialized subjects.	2.84	.793	ME
25. HUMSS-specialized subjects are not important for my life.	2.02	.942	LE
26. I'm no good in HUMSS specialized subjects.	2.37	.824	LE
27. I study the specialized subjects of the HUMSS strand because I know how useful it is.	3.05	.701	ME
28. HUMSS teachers have made me feel I have the ability to go on in HUMSS-specialized subjects.	3.09	.652	ME
29. My teachers think I'm the kind of person who could do well in HUMSS-specialized subjects.	2.89	.703	ME
Overall Mean	2.63	.311	ME

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Favorable to a great extent (GE) 2.50 – 3.49 Favorable to a moderate extent (ME) 1.50 – 2.49 Favorable to a little extent (LE); 1.00 – 1.49 Favorable to a very little extent (VLE)

Table 7 presents the respondents' attitudes toward the HUMSS-specialized subjects. It exposed that the attitude has a total mean rating of 2.63 (SD = .311), which is qualitatively described as favorable to a moderate extent". It indicates that the respondents have high attitudes. The students need Humanities and Social Sciences for their future

work (M=3.40, SD=.735). They think that they surely learn HUMSS specialized subjects (M=3.35, SD=.616), and they believe that knowing its concept will help them earn a living (M=3.22, SD=.545). Having a high attitude towards a subject means holding strong positive feelings and interest in that topic. It involves enthusiasm, motivation, and eagerness to

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learn more, leading to greater engagement and, ultimately, higher achievement (WiserRead, 2024).

Moreover, based on the responses provided by senior high school students regarding their attitudes toward Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) specialized subjects through an interview, the attitudes of SHS learners toward HUMSS-specialized subjects reveal a nuanced range of confidence, motivation, and perceived relevance to their future careers. Responses illustrate a spectrum of self-assurance: some students express strong confidence, such as those who cite enjoyment in learning and positive feedback from previous successes. For instance, one student stated, "I feel quite confident in my ability to learn and excel in HUMSS-specialized subject due to my critical thinking analysis and writing," highlighting past achievements as a source of confidence. Conversely, other students admit a lack of confidence but are eager to improve; one student said, "*I am not really confident in my ability kasi po wala akong tiwala pero willing po akong matuto at mapalawak pa ang aking kaalaman sa mga specialize subjects,*" (I am not really confident in my ability because I have no trust in myself, but I am willing to learn and expand my knowledge in the specialized subjects), reflecting a willingness to grow despite current insecurities.

Regarding teacher engagement, learners overwhelmingly stated that teachers' interest positively impacts their motivation and engagement. Responses such as, "*Ang interes na ipinapakita ng aking mga guro ay malaking bahagi ng aking pag-unlad sa mga espesyal na asignatura ng HUMSS,*" (The interest shown by my teachers is a significant part of my development in HUMSS-specialized subjects) suggest that personalized attention and support boost students' drive to excel. This support is crucial for maintaining high levels of motivation; as a student noted, "When teachers care about my progress, it makes me want to work harder and pay more attention in class." This demonstrates that teacher involvement plays a crucial role in students' success, with autonomous motivation and

enjoyment mediating this connection (Wang et al., 2022). Moreover, the impact of teacher interest and encouragement is highlighted as crucial in fostering motivation and engagement (Pérez-Salas et al., 2021). This positive reinforcement enhances their academic performance and strengthens their belief in the importance of continuous education for their future endeavors (Barberos et al., 2019).

In terms of career relevance, students recognize the substantial benefits of understanding HUMSS concepts for their future professions. For example, one student highlighted the practical application of skills in their chosen field, saying, "I want to be a nurse, so these subjects help me improve my communication skills and confidence to present a topic- it would help me communicate well with my patients in the future." Another emphasized the broader impact on career success, noting, "Understanding concepts in HUMSS-specialized subjects will contribute to my future career or livelihood in several ways."

Challenges related to HUMSS subjects also emerge, with students expressing concerns about essay writing and managing complex ideas. One student mentioned, "*Ang mga nagiging challenge sa akin sa mga specialize subjects ng HUMMS ay ang mga pag gawa ng essay*" (The challenges I face in HUMMS subjects include essay writing), while another worried about balancing multiple assignments.

Overall, the qualitative data shows that while SHS learners generally value HUMSS subjects for their future benefits, they grapple with varying levels of attitude and face challenges that impact their academic experience. While initial uncertainty and challenges exist in pursuing advanced HUMSS specialized subjects, students are motivated by supportive teaching environments and the belief that mastering these subjects will significantly contribute to their future success and personal growth (Johnson, 2017). Teachers' engagement plays a pivotal role in motivating students, and there is a strong recognition of how HUMSS learning can enrich both personal and professional aspects of their lives.

Section 3. Significant Difference between self-efficacy level and Attitude level when grouped according to the profile variables.

A. Significant Differences in the components of self-efficacy when grouped according to profile variables

Table 8. Difference in Self-Efficacy when Grouped according to Sex

Self Efficacy	Sex	Mean Rank	U-test	p-value
Mastery Experience	Male	39.26	731.50	.329
	Female	44.23		
Social Persuasion	Male	40.02	766.00	.531
	Female	43.30		
Vicarious Experience	Male	39.92	761.50	.501
	Female	43.42		
Physiological and Emotional States	Male	39.19	728.50	.320
	Female	44.31		

*. *The difference is significant at the 0.05 level.*

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Table 8 shows that in all aspects, female respondents have a higher mean rank computed compared to male respondents in terms of their self-efficacy. Thus, there were differences between the mean levels of the two groups of respondents. To determine whether these differences are significant, the Mann-Whitney U test for independent groups was computed. The result showed that no significant differences were observed in mastery experience (U=731.50, p-value=.329), social persuasion (U=766.00, p-value=.531),

vicarious experience (U=761.50, p-value=.501), and physiological and emotional states (U=728.50, p-value=.320) when grouped according to sex. It implies that the level of self-efficacy towards the specialized subjects in the HUMSS strand is the same for all respondents regardless of their sex. This supports the study of Barrera (2022), who found that there is no difference when comparing the self-efficacy of the learners in Social Sciences when classified by sex.

Table 9. Difference in Self-efficacy when Grouped according to Birth Order

Self Efficacy	Birth Order	Mean Rank	H-test	p-value
Mastery Experience	First Born Sibling	44.22	1.071	.585
	Middle Born Sibling	40.93		
	Youngest Born Sibling	35.75		
Social Persuasion	First Born Sibling	44.43	1.103	.576
	Middle Born Sibling	40.77		
	Youngest Born Sibling	35.75		
Vicarious Experience	First Born Sibling	41.10	.877	.645
	Middle Born Sibling	43.20		
	Youngest Born Sibling	35.55		
Physiological and Emotional States	First Born Sibling	37.87	2.613	.271
	Middle Born Sibling	41.70		
	Youngest Born Sibling	51.55		

*. The difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 9 reveals that there is no pattern in the computed mean level of self-efficacy of the respondents. First-born sibling respondent has the highest computed mean rank under mastery experience (M=44.22) and social persuasion (M=44.43).

Meanwhile, the middle-born sibling respondent has the highest computed mean rank under vicarious experience (M=41.10). The youngest-born sibling has the highest computed mean ranks under physiological and emotional states. (M=51.55).

To determine whether these differences are significant, the Kruskal-Wallis H test was computed. Results

showed that no significant differences were observed in mastery experience (H=1.071, p-value=.585), social persuasion (H=1.103, p-value=.576), vicarious experience (H=.877, p-value=.645), and physiological and emotional states (H=2.613, p-value=.271) when grouped according to birth order. This implies that the level of self-efficacy of all respondents regarding the specialized subjects in the HUMSS strand is the same regardless of their birth order. The findings are similar to the study conducted by Mazumdar & Sumathi (2022), which shows no significant difference in self-efficacy based on birth order.

Table 10. Difference in Self-Efficacy when grouped according to Family Monthly Income

Self Efficacy	Family Monthly Income	Mean Rank	H-test	p-value
Mastery Experience	43,828 & above	49.95	2.374	.499
	21,194 - 43,827	43.92		
	10,957 - 21,193	42.52		
	below 10,957	38.15		
Social Persuasion	43,828 & above	45.20	.661	.882
	21,194 - 43,827	37.17		
	10,957 - 21,193	41.78		
	below 10,957	41.74		
Vicarious Experience	43,828 & above	34.35	1.922	.589
	21,194 - 43,827	44.33		

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	10,957 - 21,193	45.88		
	below 10,957	40.25		
Physiological and Emotional States	43,828 & above	42.80	2.337	.505
	21,194 - 43,827	41.04		
	10,957 - 21,193	34.95		
	below 10,957	44.59		

*. The difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 10 shows that in mastery experience, social persuasion, and physiological and emotional states, respondents from bracket 43,828 & above have the highest mean ranks computed in terms of their self-efficacy. While in vicarious experience, respondents from bracket 10,957 - 21 193 have the highest ranks computed. Thus, there were differences between the mean levels of respondents.

To determine whether these differences are significant, the Kruskal-Wallis H test was computed. Results showed that no significant differences were observed in mastery experience (H=2.374, p-value=.499), social

persuasion (H=.661, p-value=.882), vicarious experience (H=1.922, p-value=.589), and physiological and emotional states (H=2.337, p-value=.505) when grouped according to family monthly income. This implies that the level of self-efficacy towards the specialized subjects in the HUMSS strand is the same for all respondents, regardless of their monthly incomes from their families. This is in line with the study conducted by Christy and Mythili (2020), which stated no significant difference between self-efficacy when grouped with family monthly income.

B. Difference between the level of attitude towards specialized subjects of HUMSS strand according to profile variables.

Table 11. Difference in Attitude when Grouped According to Profile Variables

Profile		Mean Rank	Test Statistic	p-value
Sex	Male	42.36	U-test 794.00	.719
	Female	40.46		
Birth Order	First Born Sibling	41.17	H-Test 2.247	.325
	Middle Born Sibling	39.29		
	Youngest Born Sibling	51.80		
Family Monthly Income	43,828 & above	36.50	H-test 3.805	.283
	21,194 - 43,827	30.83		
	10,957 - 21,193	44.98		
	below 10,957	44.21		

*. The difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 11 presents the difference between the attitudes of the respondents when grouped according to sex, birth order, and family monthly income. It can be seen that in all aspects of their profile variables, the computed p-value is greater than 0.05. Thus, there is no significant difference in their attitude when grouped to the sex (U=794.00, p-value=.719), birth order (H=2.247, p-value=.325), and family monthly income (H=3.805, p-value=.283), of the respondents. This implies that the attitudes of the respondents regarding the specialized subjects of the respondents are the same regardless of their profile variables.

This is similar to the study conducted by Ayebo and Dingel (2021), which classified the learners according to sex, where the attitudes of the learners are treated the same regardless of their sexes. The findings are in contrast to the study conducted by Effiong et al. (2023) under birth order. It was found that birth order has a significant influence on students' attitudes, where the firstborn was more likely to show positive attitudes than the younger ones. Another is in terms of family monthly income; the results contradict the study of Wen et al. (2020), which found a strong relationship between family monthly income and study attitude.

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Section 4. Significant Relationship between the self-efficacy and attitude towards specialized subjects of HUMSS strand.

Table 12. Correlation Coefficient between Self-efficacy and Attitude

Self Efficacy		Attitude	Remarks
Mastery Experience	Pearson Correlation	.342**	Reject
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
Social Persuasion	Pearson Correlation	.343**	Reject
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
Vicarious Experience	Pearson Correlation	.196	Accept
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.077	
Physiological and Emotional States	Pearson Correlation	.349**	Reject
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
Overall	Pearson Correlation	.447**	Reject
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

***. Correlation is highly significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

Table 12 reveals the coefficient correlation between self-efficacy and the attitude of the respondents toward the specialized subjects in the HUMSS strand. It can be gleaned that the computed overall has a moderately low relationship with respondents' attitudes ($r = 0.447$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.000$) but has a significant remark. It infers that the attitude of the respondents towards the specialized subjects in the HUMSS strand is dependent on their self-efficacy.

Self-efficacy was categorized into four parts: mastery experience, social persuasion, vicarious experience, and physiological and emotional states. It can be observed that mastery experience ($r = .342$, $p\text{-value} = .002$), social persuasion ($r = .343$, $p\text{-value} = .002$), and physiological and emotional states ($r = .349$, $p\text{-value} = .001$) contain a moderately low relationship but have significant remarks. It implies that their attitudes can be determined by their mastery experience, social persuasion, and physiological and emotional states.

Meanwhile, there exists no significant relationship between the vicarious experience and attitude of the respondents towards the specialized subjects in the HUMSS strand ($r = .196$, $p\text{-value} = .077$). This implies that the vicarious experience of the respondents does not determine their attitude.

This is similar to the study conducted by Yan and Leung (2018), where the self-efficacy of the learners predicts their level of attitude. Likewise, the study by Samardzic (2018) found a strong association between self-efficacy and attitude.

Section 5. Enhancing the self-efficacy and attitudes of the Senior High School learners on their specialized Subjects.

This study concluded that there is a significant relationship between respondents' self-efficacy and their attitude toward the specialized subjects in the Humanities and Social Sciences.

Based on the insights gathered from the interviews, there is a clear imperative for an enhancement program aimed at strengthening self-efficacy and fostering positive attitudes among Senior High School students toward HUMSS-specialized subjects.

The interviews revealed that students' self-efficacy levels vary widely, influenced by mastery experiences where incremental learning and deep comprehension significantly enhance confidence in handling assignments and developing critical thinking skills. Personal engagement with subjects also plays a crucial motivational role, highlighting the impact of individual interests on self-belief and academic success.

Furthermore, social persuasion, including positive feedback from teachers and peers, emerges as a significant factor in boosting students' confidence and perseverance in HUMSS subjects. Conversely, a lack of support or negative comments can diminish enthusiasm and hinder academic progress. Vicarious experiences, such as observing successful peers, inspire students to set higher academic goals and adopt effective learning strategies, reinforcing their belief in their capabilities.

Moreover, physiological and emotional states, such as anxiety and nervousness, affect students' ability to engage fully in learning activities. Effective coping mechanisms, such as mindfulness practices, are essential in managing these emotions and improving overall academic performance.

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Despite initial uncertainties and challenges, students recognize the intrinsic value of mastering HUMSS subjects for their future careers and personal growth, driven by the belief that these skills are essential across various professional fields and societal roles.

In conclusion, understanding these dynamics—mastery experiences, social persuasion, vicarious experiences, and emotional states—is crucial for designing effective educational interventions that nurture students' confidence and foster their academic success in specialized HUMSS subjects. This comprehensive approach ensures supportive learning environments that empower students to excel and contribute meaningfully to their academic and professional pursuits.

As a result, crafting an enhancement program is one of the greatest ways to enhance their self-efficacy and attitude toward the specialized subjects. Hence, Project INSPIRE (Increasing Self-efficacy and Positive Interest in Humanities and Social Sciences through Innovative Resources and Engagement) stands out as the leading initiative in this endeavor.

INSPIRE provides a customized approach to sustaining self-efficacy and positive attitudes towards specialized subjects in the humanities and social sciences. This is achieved through proper assistance, interactive workshops, and immersive learning experiences. By empowering students with the tools and self-assurance, INSPIRE aims to ignite an interest in these subjects and their practical applications. (*See Appendix L for the Learning Enhancement Program Project Proposal*).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

With the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The overall self-efficacy of the students is high, which indicates that students believe in their capability to attain good standing in the specialized subjects in HUMSS.
2. The overall attitude of the learners is high, which concludes that learners have favorable dispositions that can contribute to their academic success, enjoyment of learning, and overall satisfaction with their educational experience.
3. The attitude of the respondents towards specialized subjects in HUMSS relies on the learners' self-efficacy. Furthermore, the learners' self-efficacy under mastery experience, social persuasion, and physiological and emotional can affect their attitude. However, their attitude towards the specialized subjects can not be determined by their self-efficacy under vicarious experiences.
4. The learner's level of self-efficacy and attitudes towards the specialized subjects of HUMSS are the same regardless of their sex, birth order, and family monthly income.
5. The utilization enhancement program presents a promising approach to sustaining self-efficacy and positive attitudes among students, particularly toward specialized subjects. By disseminating information and fostering discussions on strategies for creating a supportive learning environment, educators can empower students to approach their studies with confidence, motivation, and enthusiasm. These efforts not only have the potential to enhance academic performance but also contribute to the overall well-being of students. Embracing such initiatives underscores a commitment to student success and the creation of a nurturing educational community.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions drawn, the following are recommended:

1. Given the substantial levels of self-efficacy observed among students in Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) specialized subjects, future research should concentrate on examining the specific factors that contribute to and sustain this self-belief. A qualitative investigation into the strategies and experiences that students perceive as enhancing their self-efficacy could yield deeper insights into effective educational practices. Understanding these factors could inform interventions aimed at fostering and maintaining students' self-efficacy beliefs in similar educational contexts.
2. Further exploration into the longitudinal impact of students' positive attitudes towards specialized subjects on their academic achievement and overall educational experience is recommended. By conducting a longitudinal study, researchers can monitor how sustained positive attitudes influence academic outcomes over time. This study should encompass quantitative measures of academic performance and qualitative insights into students' perceptions and experiences to gain a comprehensive understanding of the enduring benefits of positive attitudes in education.
3. There is a need for deeper investigation into the nuanced relationship between various dimensions of self-efficacy—especially mastery experience, social persuasion, and physiological/emotional states—and students' attitudes towards specialized subjects within the HUMSS strand. Using both quantitative

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and qualitative methodologies, researchers can delve into how these dimensions individually and collectively influence attitudes, thereby enhancing understanding of the interaction between self-efficacy and attitude formation.

4. Conduct a comparative analysis across diverse demographic variables—including gender, birth order, and family income—to explore potential differences or similarities in self-efficacy and attitudes towards specialized subjects within the HUMSS strand. Employing a mixed-methods approach, researchers can examine how these demographic factors interact with self-efficacy and attitudes, utilizing quantitative measures and qualitative insights from students and stakeholders.
5. Further research should investigate the effectiveness of utilization enhancement programs in sustaining and improving students' self-efficacy and positive attitudes towards specialized subjects, particularly within the HUMSS curriculum. This research should involve a comprehensive evaluation of program strategies, such as disseminating information and facilitating discussions to foster a supportive learning environment. Using mixed-methods approaches, researchers can assess quantitative outcomes like changes in self-efficacy levels and attitudes among participants, alongside qualitative insights from students, educators, and administrators about the program's impact. Additionally, exploring long-term effects on academic performance and student well-being will provide valuable insights into program sustainability and broader educational implications. Understanding these mechanisms will refine program elements to better support students and reinforce a commitment to nurturing a supportive educational community.

6. Other Recommendations:

- a. Students: They should be encouraged to engage in mastery experiences actively, seek social support and persuasion, and manage their physiological and emotional states effectively to enhance their self-efficacy and attitudes towards specialized subjects. They should also be made aware of the importance of their beliefs and capabilities to succeed in their academic pursuits. They should also be provided with resources and support systems to develop and maintain high levels of self-efficacy.
- b. Teachers: They should design instructional strategies that promote mastery experiences, provide constructive feedback, and foster a

supportive learning environment to enhance students' self-efficacy and attitudes towards specialized subjects. They should be trained in techniques for promoting self-efficacy beliefs among students and be encouraged to incorporate these strategies into their teaching practices.

- c. School administrators: They should implement interventions and programs aimed at enhancing students' self-efficacy beliefs and attitudes toward specialized subjects, particularly in the HUMSS field. Additionally, allocating resources for teacher professional development opportunities is crucial, ensuring educators are equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively support students in cultivating positive attitudes toward learning.
- d. Future researchers: They should conduct longitudinal studies to explore the long-term effects of self-efficacy beliefs and attitudes toward specialized subjects on academic performance and career outcomes. They should also investigate the role of additional factors, such as cultural influences and learning environments, in shaping students' self-efficacy beliefs and attitudes towards specialized subjects. Research focusing on developing and validating interventions aimed at enhancing self-efficacy beliefs and attitudes towards specialized subjects would contribute to the existing literature and inform educational practices.

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DEDICATION

This humble work is dedicated to the Senior High School Students of Tuao High School for the School Year 2023-2024, my loving husband, Carl Hendrick O. Rabut, and our dear son, Calvin Pierre R. Rabut.

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